

CHEMICAL CONTAMINATION IN AGRICULTURE: THE LASTING ECOLOGICAL & HEALTH EFFECTS OF PESTICIDES

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ABSTRACT

Pesticides are the natural or chemically synthesized compounds used in farming practices to protect crops from pests, weeds, and other insects. The increased use of pesticides in today's agricultural practices poses serious risks to environmental ecosystems and has increased the negative health effects on humans. Pesticides endanger higher trophic levels and result in adverse health conditions such as cancer, acute and chronic poisoning, neurological disorders, and endocrine disruption by building up in the food chain. Industrial pesticides cause soil and air pollution and put the survival of various birds, insects, and other aquatic organisms in danger by reducing their food supplies, species diversity, and impairing reproduction resulting in the population decline of animals and plants. This emphasizes the importance of striking a balance between environmental and health sustainability and agricultural productivity. This review critically examines the adverse effects of chemical pesticides on water, plants, natural systems, and human health.

Keywords: : Pesticides; farming practices; health effects; pollution.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Pesticides are the natural or chemically synthesized compounds used in today's agricultural practices to protect crops from pests, weeds, and other insects. Pesticide, by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), is defined as: any material designed to prevent, eliminate, or control any pest, such as disease-carrying insects, or unwanted plant or animal species. Furthermore, it says that these are the substances that harm or otherwise interfere with the production, processing, storage, transportation, or marketing of food, agricultural commodities, wood and wood products, or animal feedstuffs¹.

Moreover, pesticides are used to eliminate other living organisms, including vertebrates, nematodes, and arthropods like insects, which can contaminate our food supplies and cause several health issues.

Organochlorines, organophosphates, carbamates, and pyrethroids are the four general categories into which they fall; each having distinct properties and effects. Organochlorines build up in food chains and are extremely persistent in the environment and pose a threat to both public health and biodiversity. Although they are less persistent, organophosphates—which control the majority of the pesticide market—can be acutely harmful to non-target species, including people. Analogous to organophosphates, carbamates are problem-causing due to their toxic effects. On the other hand, pyrethroids are more efficient and relatively less harmful to animals.

Whereas, carbamates are problematic because of their poisonous effects. Even though the use of pesticides minimizes agricultural losses and oppose insect vector diseases, their extensive use poses significant risks to water quality, natural system (soil and aquatic), food safety, and health risks like chronic illnesses and poisoning.

This issue emphasizes how important it is to strike a balance between environmental and health sustainability and agricultural productivity². The excessive and inappropriate use of pesticides in the agriculture sector has been linked to a number of public health issues as well as environmental threats. Nonetheless, an analysis of the correlation between

the use of pesticides and the emergence of disease symptoms among farmers by exposure to dangerous pesticides in various parts of the nation revealed a noteworthy impact. “Moderately” or “highly hazardous” pesticides are used by the majority of farmers. Pesticides are typically blended with around half of the sprayers used in agricultural fields. Given that the majority of Indians (56.7%) work in the agricultural sector, they are particularly vulnerable to exposure to pesticides used in agricultural settings³. Consumption of pesticides has readily increased from 1990 to 2022, reaching up to 3.69 million tons in 2022 worldwide¹³ where Brazil was by far the largest pesticide consuming country (800.65 thousand metric tons), followed by the United States (467.68 thousand metric tons), Indonesia (294.67 thousand metric tons), and Argentina (262.51 thousand metric tons)¹⁴.

Figure 1: Showing consumption of pesticides by leading countries worldwide in 2022 (in 1,000 metric tons)

2. IMPACT OF PESTICIDES ON ENVIRONMENTAL ECOSYSTEM

The ecological footprint of pesticide use in agriculture significantly impacts the environmental ecosystems by contaminating water, soil, and air, eventually disrupting natural cycles and reducing biodiversity. The reason being their bio accumulative potential

and persistent nature which may show long term effects to short term changes in the normal functioning of an ecosystem.

Along with the helpful results pesticides that do not degrade readily gets accumulated either in soil or will move from one site to another in the form of degraded products whose toxicity depends on the physical and chemical properties of pesticides. These pesticides enter into water bodies through the runoff from the agricultural field and industrial wastewater. Close interaction between soil and water bodies makes surface water sources such as streams, lakes, and estuaries vulnerable to pesticide contamination⁴.

The geographic distribution of 92 of the most widely used agricultural pesticides is examined in a global study, published in *Nature* (2023), and found that approximately 70,000 tons of potentially hazardous chemicals leak into aquifers annually, negatively affecting ecosystems and freshwater resources. Only a fraction of pesticides enters into river systems out of which most of the active ingredients end up in the ocean having potential negative impacts on marine wildlife and coral reefs. Out of the 0.94 Tg net yearly pesticide input utilized in this study in 2015, 82% is broken down biologically, 10% stays in the soil as residue, and 7.2% seeps below the root zone.

Figure2: Showing the fate of pesticides in environment

Even though only 0.1 percent leaching into fresh waterways take place, it is sufficient to have a detrimental impact on the ecosystem⁵. Transfer of pesticides not only occurs in areas adjacent to each other but also transports over long distances. Industrial pesticides cause soil and air pollution and puts the survival of various birds, insects, and other aquatic organisms in danger by reducing their food supplies, species diversity, and impairing reproduction resulting in a population decline of animals and plants⁶.

3. IMPACT OF PESTICIDES ON HUMAN HEALTH

The groups such as production workers, formulators, sprayers, mixers, loaders and agricultural farm workers are at high risk of being exposed to pesticides. Farmers have adopted agricultural practices involving the use of hazardous pesticides to control undesired microbes during crop production, harvesting, and storage of food.

Farmers, working on fields, are most vulnerable to chronic exposure of pesticides leading to various chronic diseases such as hypertension, diabetes etc. Workers, in industrial settings, are also at increased risk as they handle toxic chemicals used in the production of pesticides. Pesticides not only compromise the crop productivity and fertility but also affects human health directly or indirectly².

When pesticides are produced and applied, human occupational exposure is expected, but the broader public can also be exposed to biological concentration through the food chain, drift, and contamination of food and water sources⁷.

As we move along the food chain, pesticide concentration gets magnified and enters into aquatic organisms making it unfit for human consumption⁴. Chronic ingestion of pesticides affects human's body hormones causing reduced body immunity, reproductive abnormalities, hormonal imbalance, carcinogenic effects and diminished intelligence in the children under the body development stage⁸. Other symptoms that can be seen in people exposed to such hazardous chemicals include asthma, chronic sinus problems, migraines, skin diseases, allergies and autoimmune diseases⁹. Long term, neurobehavioral deficits and depression is caused by acute poisoning of organophos

phases. However, it is unclear how low dose exposures would affect health without clinical poisoning¹⁰. Moreover, investigations have linked amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, Alzheimer's syndrome, and other dementias with pesticides notably organochlorine and organophosphate, with the most consistent discoveries with Parkinson's disease¹¹.

The increasing use of pesticides, in addition to widespread human exposure during production, application and through various environmental pathways, underlines how essential it is to thoroughly understand the risks associated with these chemicals. It is vital to take into account their benefits because of their potential to leading in development of many diseases and adverse health impacts. Newly created, insecticides must also undergo comprehensive health hazard studies before using them extensively.

Hazardous pesticides are frequently replaced by chemicals with fewer details on their long-term wellness, as in the case with many current chemicals. Additional studies must look at the cumulative and associated effects of continued exposure to various pesticides in addition to assessing specific active components and formulations¹². Awareness initiatives must be stepped up in the interim to educate the public—especially those who are the most vulnerable to the dangers of pesticide exposure and to put measures into effect that restrict or eliminate human interaction. Furthermore, to reduce pesticide dependence globally, especially among developing nations, agricultural sustainability and vector control strategies must be developed, enhanced, and imposed immediately.

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4. REFERENCES

1. Understanding the context | Pest and Pesticide Management | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations | IPM and Pesticide Risk Reduction | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (n.d.). <https://www.fao.org/pest-and-pesticide-management/about/understanding-the-context/en/>
2. Kumar, M., Yadav, A. N., Saxena, R., Paul, D., & Tomar, R. S. (2020). Biodiversity of pesticides degrading microbial communities and their environmental impact. *Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology*, 31(1-3), 101883. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcab.2020.101883>
3. Abhilash, P. C., & Singh, N. (2009). Pesticide use and application: an Indian scenario. *Journal of hazardous materials*, 165(1-3), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2008.10.061>
4. Sharma, A., Kumar, V., Shahzad, B., Tanveer, M., Sidhu, G. P. S., Handa, N., Kohli, S. K., Yadav, P., Bali, A. S., Parihar, R. D., Dar, O. I., Singh, K., Jasrotia, S., Bakshi, P., Ramakrishnan, M., Kumar, S., Bhardwaj, R., & Thukral, A. K. (2019). Worldwide pesticide usage and its impacts on ecosystem. *SN Applied Sciences*, 1(11), 1-2. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-019-1485-1>
5. Maggi, F., Tang, F. H. M., & Tubiello, F. N. (2023). Agricultural pesticide land budget and river discharge to oceans. *Nature*, 620(7976), 1013–1017. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06296-x>
6. Pathak, V. M., Verma, V. K., Rawat, B. S., Kaur, B., Babu, N., Sharma, A., Dewali, S., Yadav, M., Kumari, R., Singh, S., Mohapatra, A., Pandey, V., Rana, N., & Cunill, J. M. (2022). Current status of pesticide effects on environment, human health and its eco-friendly management as bioremediation: A comprehensive review. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 13, 1-2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.962619>
7. Blair, A., Ritz, B., Wesseling, C., & Freeman, L. B. (2014). Pesticides and human health. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 72(2), 81–82. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oemed-2014-102454>
8. Yadav, I. C., Devi, N. L., Syed, J. H., Cheng, Z., Li, J., Zhang, G., & Jones, K. C. (2014). Current status of persistent organic pesticides residues in air, water, and soil, and

their possible effect on neighboring countries: A comprehensive review of India. *The Science of the Total Environment*, 511, 123–137.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.12.041>

9. Shekhar, C., Khosya, R., Thakur, K., Mahajan, D., Kumar, R., Kumar, S., & Sharma, A. K. (2024). A systematic review of pesticide exposure, associated risks, and Long-Term human health impacts. *Toxicology Reports*, 13, 2, 101840.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxrep.2024.101840>

10. Weisenburger, D. D. (1993). Human health effects of agricultural use. *Human Pathology*, 24(6), 571–576.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0046-8177\(93\)90234-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0046-8177(93)90234-8)

11. Mostafalou, S., & Abdollahi, M. (2013). Pesticides and human chronic diseases: Evidences, mechanisms, and perspectives. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*, 268(2), 157–177.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2013.01.025>

12. Solecki, R., Stein, B., Frische, T., Matezki, S., Wogram, J., & Streloke, M. (2014). Paradigm shift in the risk assessment of cumulative effects of pesticide mixtures and multiple residues to humans and wildlife: German proposal for a new approach. *Journal of Consumer Protection and Food Safety*, 9(4), 329–331.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00003-014-0914-8>

13. Statista research department (2024b). Global pesticide agricultural use 1990-2022.

<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1263077/global-pesticide-agricultural-use/#:~:text=From%201990%20to%202022%2C%20the%20worldwide%20agricultural%20use,increased%2C%20reaching%203.69%20million%20metric%20tons%20in%202022>

14. Statista research department (2024). Global pesticide agricultural use 2022, by leading country.

<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1263069/global-pesticide-use-by-country/>